

Forward Propagation Geometrical Optics and Beam Steering

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1 Introduction

The interaction of EM waves with the earth's ionosphere, as documented in [Wil21], has been studied for more than a century. Under the assumption that the divergence of the electric field is negligible, the time-harmonic form of Maxwell's equation can be manipulated to construct a vector wave equation involving only the electric field and a constitutive relation. However, the essential elements for computation are captured by the scalar wave equation, which characterizes propagation in the earth's atmosphere, sound propagation in the earth's oceans, and acoustic propagation in the earth's surface. We introduce the scalar wave equation with two equivalent representations:

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \nabla_{\perp}^2 + k^2 \right] \psi(x; \eta) = -k^2 X(x; \eta) \quad (1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \nabla_{\perp}^2 + k^2 K(x; \eta) \right] \psi(x; \eta) = 0 \quad (2)$$

where $K(x; \eta) = \sqrt{n(\mathbf{r})} = 1 + X(x; \eta)$ and $k = 2\pi f/c$, where c is the vacuum velocity of light. In its simplest ionospheric form $X(x; \eta) = -(\omega_p/\omega)^2$ where the plasma frequency, ω_p , is proportional to electron density and $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the radian frequency. Identifying axial and transverse coordinates explicitly anticipates directional propagation. For example, if $X = 0$ it is readily shown that the operator

$$\Theta_{\Delta x}(\psi(x, \eta)) = \int \exp\{2\pi i(k\sqrt{1 - (\kappa/k)^2}\Delta x + \kappa) \cdot \eta\} \widehat{\psi}(x; \kappa) \frac{d\kappa}{(2\pi)^2} \quad (3)$$

where $\widehat{\psi}(x; \kappa)$ is the two-dimensional Fourier transform of $\psi(x, \eta)$, advances a field at x to $x + \Delta x$.

Upon introducing the free-space Green's function, (1) can be written as an equivalent integro differential equation, which can be used to incrementally advance a known field in an inhomogeneous medium. Formally,

$$\psi(x + \Delta x, \eta) = \Theta_{\Delta x}(\psi_0(\eta)) + k^2 \int_0^{\infty} \int \psi(x', \eta') X(x'; \eta') G(k|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|) dx' d\eta' \quad (4)$$

where $G(k|\mathbf{r}|)$ is the free-space Green function and $\psi_0(\eta)$ is the initiating field at $x = 0$. An immediate problem is accommodating waves initiated by induced sources beyond $x = 0$. The forward approximation neglects these contributions by truncating the x' integration at x .

Constructing a tractable marching formulation remains. In recently published papers [RC21a] and [RC21b] and earlier results cited in the papers we used the fact that if the product term $\psi(x', \eta') X(x'; \eta')$ is removed from the integral, the remaining integration over the Green's function has a well-known analytic form. The forward propagation equation (FPE) results:

$$\psi(x + \Delta x, \eta) = \Theta_{\Delta x}(\psi(x, \eta)) - ik\Delta x/2X(x; \eta)\psi(x, \eta) \quad (5)$$

However, as shown in [RC21b], propagation of a narrow HF beam refracted by a Chapman layer produced trajectories that did not match ray trace results. A complete treatment of propagation was presented in a series of papers by Louis Fishman, most recently [Fis02]. The development proceeds from the second form of the wave equation 2. A key finding, which has been recognized in the acoustic community for some time, is that free-propagation and media-interaction contributions cannot be incrementally separated as the forward approximation and (5) imply. Indeed, attempts to integrate (5) as written lead to numerical instability. The implementation invariably uses

$$\psi(x + \Delta x, \eta) = \Theta_{\Delta x}(\psi(x, \eta)) \exp\{-ik\Delta x/2X(x; \eta)\} \quad (6)$$

We recognize that the principal results from the theory propagation in random media can be constructed with multiple-phase-screen methods. This is a consequence of the fact the theory of propagation in random media is restricted to narrow-angle scattering. The point is made in a seminal paper by Roger Dashen [Das79]. Conventional multiple-phase-screen methods can be applied in environments that do not generate significant refractive bending.

2 Ray Optics and Operator Methods

Complete propagation theories proceed from the second form of the wave equation (2). Ray optics assumes a generalized plane-wave solution with slow amplitude variations. For scalar fields geometric optics ray theory takes a particularly simple form:

$$\frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}}{ds^2} + \frac{dn}{nds} \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{ds} = \frac{\nabla n}{n}, \quad (7)$$

where s is the path distance. A ray calculation is initiated by a starting point and a direction. A bundle of rays characterizes the propagation of a focused beam, with ray density variations quantitatively related to the beam peak intensity. Phase fronts traced by surfaces of constant optical path length.

Beyond ray tracing, there are few operator methods that generate tractable results. A result by Fishman [FMW87], which seems to have been rediscovered by Ostachev [OMW19] is intuitively appealing:

$$\Theta_{\Delta x}(\psi(x, \eta)) = \int \exp\{2\pi i(k\sqrt{K(x, \eta) - (\kappa/k)^2 \Delta x} + \kappa) \cdot \eta\} \hat{\psi}(x; \kappa) \frac{d\kappa}{(2\pi)^2} \quad (8)$$

In effect the homogeneous refractive index in the free-space propagation operator is replaced by $K(x, \eta)$. Direct integration requires an integration over all spatial wavenumbers at each altitude, which is prohibitive for large-scale problem. However, a columnated beam has a finite support in both the spatial and spatial-frequency domains. Moreover, the altitude integrations can be evaluated in parallel. Additionally, the full calculation is necessary only in the ionosphere. As a test of the Fishman Locally Homogeneous Wave Extension (LHWE), a segment of the 10 MHz Chapman-layer problem introduced in [RC21a] and [RMBC19] was evaluated.

Figure (3) shows the intensity variation of a propagating field initiated by a focused beam truncated at the 50 km intercept. The imposed phase variation is derived from a point on the circular earth surface (shown in green). The source point is chosen for a central ray intercept at 32 degrees. Defining ray traces from a ± 1 -degree ray bundle are overlaid. The field minimum and the ray convergence coincide with very good overall agreement. Figure (2) shows the corresponding field spectral intensity. There is very good agreement between the ray-trace results and confining range of both the beam intensity and its spectral intensity. Ray-trace results necessarily do not defined the wavefield. Consequently agreement is a necessary but not sufficient condition for validation.

Figure 1. LHFE calculation of beam intensity launched into Chapman layer with ray-trace bundle overlaid.

Whereas are previous ray-trace comparisons only condered the central height and direction as compared to the peak field intensity height and peak spectral intensity angle. Figure 4 shows the variation of the optical path relative to the optical path of the central ray. Constant phase surfaces are are normal to contours of constant optical path, which can be converted to path-integrated phase, effectively HF TEC. At this juncture ray-trace measurements are complementary. Both operator and wide-angle parabolic differential equation methods are being pursued.

Figure 2. LHF calculation of SDF launched into Chapman layer with ray-trace bundle overlaid.

Figure 3. LHF calculation of SDF launched into Chapman layer with ray-trace bundle overlaid.

Figure 4. Ray trace optical path variation for narrow beam initiated from a point on the surface.

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